

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ST. JOHN****FIRST NAME: ZENI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2021 on MacOS Big Sur version 11.6)

Six key concepts in this response paper

- 1) Navigating the Euclid Response Paper Template (Cleenewerck 2016)
- 2) Drafting an Essay Plan (EUCLID 2024, 7-8)
- 3) Utilizing First Person in Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 14)
- 4) Key Differences Between American and British English (EUCLID 2024, 31-32)
- 5) Plagiarism, In-Text Citations, and Paraphrasing (EUCLID 2024, 34 – 36)
- 6) Developing Style Guides as Freelance Writers (EUCLID 2024, 42)

NAVIGATING KEY CONCEPTS IN THE EUCLID UNIVERSITY COURSEPACKET

7) INTRODUCTION

The Period One coursepack provides an overview of fundamental concepts and specific requirements to meet Euclid University's general submission criteria. The insights gained from the coursepack, coupled with Professor Laurent Cleenewerck's explanatory video on how to use the Response Paper (RP) Template, will serve as a foundational guide for success in this academic program regarding the technical aspects of formatting and submission. This information will be invaluable across all courses undertaken during the pursuit of this degree as it provides clarity and guidance on how to structure my papers. I appreciate that these fundamental topics were addressed in the first period of the first course.

While some of the information presented in the readings and videos reinforced concepts I was already familiar with, certain topics, such as the recommendation to develop personal style guides as freelance writers, were novel. Despite holding a Master of Science

in Professional Writing, this is the first time I have encountered this advice, and I intend to incorporate it into my professional practice. Other information served as a refresher, including key differences between American and British English and information on plagiarism and referencing one's work.

In my response paper, I will discuss six key concepts that I consider particularly noteworthy from the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one coursepack and Professor Cleenwerck's tutorial video. The key concepts include navigating the Euclid response paper template, drafting an essay plan, using the first person in essay writing, American versus British English, plagiarism, and developing style guides.

8) NAVIGATING THE EUCLID RESPONSE PAPER TEMPLATE

The EUCLID response paper template contains pre-set formatting that aligns with the University's expectations of what stylistic choices all submitted papers should adhere to. Professor Cleenewerck's video tutorial comprehensively demonstrates this RP Template and its formatting features in Microsoft Word (Cleenewerck 2016). The template is a convenient alternative to having a style guide document that prescribes what students should adhere to and requires them to implement those guidelines themselves.

I found the customized formatting bar on the 'Home' tab of the RP Template, which Professor Cleenewerck demonstrated instrumental (Cleenewerck 2016). When utilized correctly, this template ensures consistency and efficiency in formatting various sections of the response papers without any guesswork or relying on retentive memory. Following Professor Cleenewerck's advice, I have downloaded the template, personalized it with my details, and saved it for continuous use in drafting future response papers. I also used one version of that saved template for today's assignment and found the template easy to navigate and the various formatting settings agreeable.

9) DRAFTING AN ESSAY PLAN

EUCLID (EUCLID 2024, 7) recommends the essay plan as one of the preliminary steps to drafting an essay to help organize my thoughts, clarify the research topic, and structure key arguments before writing. The section acknowledged that there is no rigidly linear approach to writing an essay, so technically, there is room to accommodate both writing aids – an outline and an essay plan (EUCLID 2024, 7). The coursepack highlights the utility of an essay plan, noting that it provides clarity on the questions that need to be addressed and the necessary research content (EUCLID 2024, 7).

Initially, I had likened the essay plan prescribed by EUCLID as similar to the essay outline I usually prepare when commencing a new writing assignment. However, I realized that the essay plan is more comprehensive. The essay plan is only developed after reading relevant material, conducting research, and reviewing and prioritizing the information

gathered. Then, that information is organized in the proposed order the essay will follow (EUCLID 2024, 9 – 10). Therefore, the essay plan serves as both a structure and a framework that will guide the actual writing of the essay.

10) UTILIZING FIRST PERSON IN ESSAY WRITING

The coursepack section titled "Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper" (EUCLID 2024, 12) provided useful guidance on maintaining focus, the importance of stating the thesis early, and the necessity of substantiating assertions with evidence. I was particularly surprised by the recommendation that academic writing should utilize the first-person singular perspective (EUCLID 2024, 14). The previous academic advice I received was to avoid first-person pronouns in scholarly, professional, and academic writing. This new perspective challenges my previous understanding and highlights a more flexible approach to academic writing. Writing in the first person will certainly take some getting used to. This initial response paper serves as a first attempt to incorporate first-person pronouns into my writing. I have found that I have had to make some amendments in subsequent iterations of my paper, as in some sections, I had reverted to writing in the third person.

11) KEY DIFFERENCES BETWEEN AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

As a dual citizen of England and Nigeria who grew up studying an American curriculum and then attending universities in the United States, with development and government clients from different countries, I frequently switch between the two language systems depending on the context. Professor Cleenewerck's explanatory video served as a timely reminder to maintain consistency in my writing style to avoid mixing conventions unintentionally (Cleenewerck 2016). While this may not be possible across various work projects, it is certainly possible within each document, and I will work hard to maintain that consistency.

I took particular interest in the key differences highlighted in the course pack as they are relevant to my work and something of note for my academic writing. While I am aware of the spelling differences, it was only through the descriptions provided in the course pack that I realized my punctuation has not always aligned with the chosen system (EUCLID 2024, 31). I also noticed that in Nigeria, many times, the punctuation does not align with the spelling conventions, and sometimes, both spellings are frequently used in documents that have multiple authors. As a copyeditor, part of what I often do requires standardizing the language – including the spelling and grammar usage – so being reminded of the key differences is helpful.

A notable revelation was when Professor Cleenewerck noted around the 8-minute mark of the tutorial video that UK punctuation places the period after the closing quotation mark, unlike the American style, which places it within the quotation marks (Cleenewerck

2016). The highlights of the key differences will remind me to maintain consistency and stick to one type of English – at least within each document.

12) PLAGIARISM, IN-TEXT CITATIONS, AND PARAPHRASING

Plagiarism is an important subject that can never be overemphasized, particularly in academia and for students pursuing research-focused degrees. Therefore, the chapter on plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34) was a welcome reminder of its definition and when credit should always be given to an author - always! The discussion on plagiarism reinforced the importance of academic integrity and proper citation practices. In my estimation, one of the most important principles to remember is that even when the writer paraphrases, they are still required to cite their sources (EUCLID 2024, 34).

The course material went further to provide definitions of paraphrasing and direct quotations, giving clear examples and emphasizing the necessity of attributing sources appropriately (EUCLID 2024, 35 – 37). Additionally, it highlighted best practices for integrating in-text citations to maintain credibility and avoid unintentional plagiarism and how to format direct quotations using the Quote Style setting on the EUCLID template (EUCLID 2024, 35).

13) DEVELOPING STYLE GUIDES AS FREELANCE WRITERS

One of the most unexpected yet valuable pieces of advice from the course material was the recommendation to develop personal style guides as freelance writers (EUCLID 2024, 41). Despite my extensive background in professional writing, both academically and professionally, I had not previously considered this approach. I am used to implementing the style guides of my clients where they exist and utilizing my stylistic norms informally where they do not. However, I plan to incorporate this advice by developing and maintaining a personalized style guide, which will help to ensure consistency in language, formatting, and citation practices across different writing projects. I intend to implement this strategy in my professional work to enhance efficiency and coherence.

14) CONCLUSION

The insights I have gained from the Period One Course Packet and Professor Cleenwerck's instructional video have been a good refresher on academic writing and stylistic conventions. It has provided a strong foundation on what structures and principles to apply across all academic writing for the duration of this degree. While I was surprised that the content was primarily focused on report writing, as I was expecting more degree-

related information, I appreciated the clarity on the expectations for future submissions. The information provided will be an essential reference throughout my academic journey at Euclid University and was quite instructive. I look forward to delving deeper into the other material and progressing with the course.

REFERENCES

Cleenwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenwerck, Laurent, Director, 2021. ACA-401 Tutorial. Vimeo.

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